

Implementation of core values for quality assurance strategy at Mathla'ul Anwar University, Banten

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Abstract

The problem in this research is the poor quality assurance strategy which means that the quality at the Anwar Banten Matlaul College is not optimal. The aim of this research is to develop a quality assurance strategy to improve academic quality in the Matlaul Anwar Banten college environment. The method used in this research is Core Values. This is a qualitative research model with several stages. The first stage is a case study using a qualitative research model. The second stage involved observation to obtain data through interviews. The third stage is observation, study of documents and recordings. The results of the research are in the form of strategic planning for quality assurance based on research, analysis of facts, resource capabilities, financial sources, determining quality standards, determining alternative actions and decision making methods. Preparation of work programs based on khithah, university statutes, management guidebooks, implementation rules, vision, mission and organizational goals. The college's work organization applies modern management concepts, organizational structure, division of tasks has been arranged and arranged based on responsibility, authority and workload. Supervision of work through a control and evaluation process. If there are errors or deviations, corrections will be made. The basic values for preparing quality assurance are in the form of Mathla'ul Anwar Banten's sermons.

Keywords: Implementation; core values; strategy

INTRODUCTION

Quality assurance strategies in an institution need to be maximized, so that the quality of graduate products from an educational institution is of a quality that meets the quality standards of education, society and the world of work. Quality assurance is designed to prevent errors from the start of the production process so as to produce products that meet specifications from the start of the education process (Jennings et al., 2020). Mathlaul Anwar College from the start has established values which are the basis for charity known as Khithah Mathalaul Anwar. The basis for this implementation contains basic values (core values) which become a reference in the implementation of education within the Mathlaul Anwar Pandeglang Banten College (Esteva-Socias et al., 2019). Basic values or core values in religious organizations are the characteristics of the organization both in the form of basic concepts and implementation (Chan et al., 2017). In Indonesia, there are known religious organizations such as Nahdlatul Ulama, Muhammadiyah, Islamic Association and Mathlaul Anwar (Coker et al., 2018) Each organization has activities in the field of education, including Mathlaul Anwar (Alam et al., 2014). The basic values of the organization will color its activities and have uniqueness and diversity (Fecher et al., 2023). Indonesia there are known religious organizations such as Nahdlatul Ulama, Muhammadiyah, Islamic Association and Mathlaul Anwar. Each organization has activities in the field of education, including Mathlaul Anwar. The basic values of the organization will color its activities and have uniqueness and diversity (Nasser Alsubaie, 2023). The development of a quality-oriented education system for the Indonesian nation is a constitutional mandate. Therefore, it is imperative for the government to carry out this mandate in order to face global demands. The rapid pace of globalization that is entering borderless areas requires the appearance and role of quality human beings (Pedro et al., 2023). Globalization challenges Indonesian people to be able to demonstrate their existence and integration amidst increasingly fierce competition in the international arena (Bauer et al., 2019).

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The discussion about the quality of education will never end. In fact, it is increasingly interesting to discuss and challenging to implement. Since 2003, when the Indonesian nation is a constitutional mandate. Therefore, it is imperative for the government to carry out this mandate in order to face global demands. The rapid pace of globalization that is entering borderless areas requires the appearance and role of quality human beings (Pedro et al., 2023). Globalization challenges Indonesian people to be able to demonstrate their existence and integration amidst increasingly fierce competition in the international arena (Bauer et al., 2019).

The discussion about the quality of education will never end. In fact, it is increasingly interesting to discuss and challenging to implement. Since 2003, when the Indonesian nation issued Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, our nation has shown a good response, and it must be realized immediately with commitment (Bodur et al., 2023). This law contains the vision, mission, functions and objectives of national education, as well as national education development strategies, to realize quality education, relevant to community needs, and competitive in global life (Ta et al., 2023). Globalization requires Indonesian people to be ready and able to compete in all borderless regions. As the main source of production factors, building quality human resources is certainly a challenge in itself. Moreover, recently the Indonesian nation is experiencing quite worrying conditions regarding the quality of education (Dal Bello et al., 2023). Even though there are children of the nation who have succeeded in achieving international achievements, and that is a matter of pride, the majority of students have not shown the expected achievements (Kuwornu et al., 2023).

Madrasas should be a place where all students can learn well. In other words, madrasas must be fair institutions by providing the opportunity to get the same education (equality of opportunity) both in quality and quantity for every student (Matson, 1998). Madrasas are expected to play an important role in the intellectual, emotional and spiritual formation of children (Rumsfeld & Masoudi, 2004). Madrasas should be a place to cultivate the intelligence of every student, and above all, ensure that every student gets equal and decent learning opportunities (Tassara, 1999). Culture is the soul of the madrasah which gives meaning to every madrasah educational activity and is a bridge between the activities and the results achieved. Culture is the condition that leads madrasah students to exceed the limits of human deficiencies to a high level of creativity, art and intellectualism. Culture is also a vehicle to transform educational values. This culture is a learning culture, which must be built from the start so that all components of the madrasa are committed to advancing the madrasa. The quality assurance system in madrasas is based on core values, at least several conditions are needed so that learning outcomes in madrasas are of superior quality, namely choose a reliable and appropriate quality assurance strategic plan. Preparing work programs, work organization and work supervision have an important role in achieving maximum learning value (Rumsfeld & Masoudi, 2004). The basic values (core values) that make up the quality assurance strategy are prepared and implemented in madrasa activities so that the basic values provide good quality

educational results. From these several conditions, quality assurance can be implemented and the implementation of madrasa quality assurance within the Menes Center Mathla'ul Anwar College environment includes three things, namely; (1) internal quality assurance carried out by the institution, in this case the Menes Center Mathla'ul Anwar College, (2) external quality assurance carried out by certain parties appointed by the institution, and (3) accreditation carried out by the school accreditation body, as the party who has the authority to carry out the school/madrasah accreditation process.

Planning is an activity that will be carried out in the future to achieve the desired goal. The planning element contains several things, namely (a) a number of activities determined previously, (b) the existence of a process, (c) the results to be achieved, (d) concerns the future at a certain time. Planning describes what will be done in the future. Planning can be described as a well defined course of future action. In planning, it is prepared regarding (a) Objectives of planning, (b) Benefits of planning, (c) Elements or components of planning (Aarsand et al., 2011). Planning is an initial activity to design what will be done in the future within a certain time (Dokova et al., 2019). Each educational unit carries out planning of the learning process, implementation of the learning process, assessment of learning outcomes, and supervision of the learning process for the implementation of an effective and efficient learning process. Namely planning the learning process where the planning of the learning process includes a syllabus and a learning implementation plan which contains at least learning objectives, teaching materials, teaching methods, learning resources and assessment of learning outcomes (Unemo et al., 2009).

Strategic planning includes the formulation of strategic preparations that will be taken as company policy to achieve goals. Strategic planning enables the formulation of long-term priorities and institutional changes based on rational considerations. Strategy must be based on customer groups and their varying expectations, then develop policies and plans that can lead the agency to achieving the organization's mission and vision (Sprott et al., 2020). Organizations are formed to achieve goals, so there must be someone who defines and conveys the meaning of achieving the organization's goals (Ishikura, 2008). Goals are defined as future conditions that a company desires and tries to realize. A plan is a blueprint used to achieve goals and determine the allocation of resources, time, tasks, and other necessary actions (Brown et al., 2014). Goals determine future goals, while plans determine the means used in the present. The concept of planning (planning) usually includes both concepts and is defined as an action to determine the company's goals to be achieved (Lasky, 2005).

Vision is an idealization of thoughts about the future of an organization which is a key force for organizational change that creates an advanced and anticipatory organizational culture and behavior towards global competition. A good vision has the main objectives, namely (1) clarifying the general direction of organizational policy change (2) motivating employees to act in the right direction (3) assisting the process of coordinating certain actions of different people (Fecher et al., 2023). The

mission is the basis of the company's existence, at the top of the goal hierarchy. The mission describes the values, ideals and basis of the company's existence. A clearly defined mission is the basis for setting goals and future plans. A mission statement is a general description of the goals that differentiate a company from other similar companies. The right mission statement can increase employee motivation and company performance. Mission is the main purpose and activity that makes an organization have a distinctive identity, while distinguishing it from other organizations operating in a similar business field (Brown et al., 2014).

According to Olasehinde-Williams (2002) when punishment is used to vent the anger of the punisher, it is administered out of proportion to the offender. Rather than reduce the frequency of the occurrence of the behaviour therefore, such punishment may lead to hostility or resentment of authority on the part of the student. Also, students who are severely punished become extremely timid, afraid or hateful of the person who punished them and may respond by running away or withdrawing from class activities. Such students may even come to learn that physical force is an acceptable way of settling conflicts especially with junior ones (Olasehinde-Williams, 2002). According to the African Child Policy Forum (ACPF, 2014), corporal punishment has a negative impact on the physical, psychological and emotional harm of students which can cause poor performance, absence from school, fear of teachers and school, dropout from school for fear of getting beaten, declining self-worth or self-esteem.

METHOD

The method with a qualitative approach in this research was chosen because symptoms, information and events, and statements from observations during the research process regarding "core value-based quality assurance strategies at Mathloul Anwar College", would be more appropriate if expressed in the form of words with data what is obtained is deeper and more correct. The main aim of this research is to improve the quality of higher education standards in a better direction. The reason for choosing the Matloul Anwar organization is that it is the largest organization in Pandeglang district. Therefore, qualitative research does not emphasize generalization but rather emphasizes meaning. The use of descriptive methods with a qualitative approach in this research was also determined on the basis of a philosophical basis which refers to the philosophy of naturalism and progressivism is research method is a case study design with a qualitative research approach, where the research procedure produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from interviews with people and the behavior of people observed. The method used is research directly observing the object that is the target of the research, namely the core value-based quality assurance strategy at Madrasah Aliyah (MA) Mathloul Anwar College, Menes Pandeglang Center. This research process includes several phases, namely (1) researcher as subject, (2) theoretical paradigm and point of view, (3) research strategy, namely a case study of core value-based quality assurance strategies at Madrasah Aliyah (MA) Mathloul Anwar College,

Menes Center, (4) Methods of data collection and analysis, through interviews, observations, artifacts, documents, notes, visuals, personal experiences, data processing, and textual analysis, (5) Art of Interpretation and Presentation, including criteria for assessing adequacy, art and interpretation strategies and writing as interpretation. This research will be carried out using a qualitative descriptive research method, which describes the meaning of research data in a systematic, factual and accurate manner. Sukmadinata, explained that research using descriptive methods is aimed at describing or illustrating existing phenomena, both natural phenomena and human engineering. This qualitative descriptive method is intended to study and solve problems in the field, through an investigation process with narrative, analysis and classification. This method is often referred to as the analytical method. Qualitative research is aimed at understanding social phenomena from the participant's point of view or perspective. Participants are people who are interviewed and observed.

RESULTS

Quality assurance strategy planning

Strategic planning is prepared in Mathloul Anwar's Khithah, Mathloul Anwar's College Statutes, a guidebook for managing MA education units and implementing regulations at Madrasah Aliyah MA. This preparation is based on a shared commitment to realizing the vision, mission and goals of the MA organization.

Madrasah Aliyah's educational commitment to creating quality and superior education is outlined in the vision and mission of Madrasah Aliyah (MA) Matloul Anwar Menes Center. The vision is to create education that is superior in achievement, religious in attitude and becomes the choice of society. The superior indicator is having qualities that are oriented towards the quality of good graduates with mastery of science and technology as well as faith and piety. Religious means having piety, being tough and always upholding Islamic values, faith and piety as the basis of attitude. To be the people's choice, that is, to be recognized, accepted and needed by all levels of society. Planning for the organization's mission is (1) organizing a learning process with an insight into excellence, both in the academic and non-academic fields, (2) creating a learning climate based on faith and piety, (3) making the community a partner and working capital for the madrasah. The mission description of Madrasah Aliyah is (1) increasing the application of participatory management, (2) developing a spirit of excellence in the fields of religion, culture, science, technology and skills throughout the academic community, (3) optimizing the implementation of active, creative, effective and enjoyable learning and cohesiveness (team teaching) to prevent vacancies in class hours, (4) implementing evaluation or assessment of learning outcomes consistently and continuously, (5) optimizing the implementation of improvement and enrichment programs, (6) optimizing guidance in the creation of written work or scientific work, (7) motivating and helping students to recognize their potential by providing a platform for extracurricular activities, (8) optimizing coaching for groups

interested in Mathematics, Physics, Biology, Chemistry, Astronomy, Economics and Computers to face Olympic competitions and model student competitions, (9) increasing the discipline and responsibility of madrasah stakeholders, (10) improving the welfare of human resources as a whole, (11) fostering and developing cooperation with the environment, (12) optimizing appreciation of religious values to become a source of wisdom in acting and behaving.

The expected objectives of the implementation at Madrasah Aliyah Mathlul Anwar Menes Center are (1) increasing students' faith and devotion as well as knowledge, especially in the field of science and technology, (2) students are expected to have broad insight in the field of science and technology, (3) increasing students' abilities as members of society in establishing social and cultural relations and the natural surroundings that are imbued with Islamic values, (4) making Madrasah Aliyah Mathlul Anwar Menes Center a model in the development of science and technology and IMTAQ for other madrasahs, (5) achieving high academic achievements good for alumnus of Madrasah Aliyah Mathlul Anwar Menes Center while at University.

Preparation of work program

The preparation of the school work program is prepared by the Madrasah Head and the school staff in accordance with the achievements and work targets to be achieved. The work program prepared refers to the vision and mission of the Madrasah, and is also guided by the principles and Khithah of Mathlul Anwar's organization. The work program is directed towards modern and technological Madrasah education. The Mathla'ul Anwar College educational program consists of: Educational programs oriented towards life skills and professional education programs aimed at readiness to apply expertise/skills in a particular field.

The Madrasah education program aims to; (a). increase students' knowledge to continue their education at a higher level and to develop themselves in line with developments in science, technology and the arts; (b). Improving students' abilities as members of society in establishing reciprocal relationships with the social, cultural and natural surroundings.

The targets for the learning implementation work program at Madrasah Aliyah Mathlul Anwar Menes Center are (1) passing one hundred percent of the National Examination, (2) increasing the proportion of graduates accepted at State Universities, (3) having a Science and Technology group ready to take part in the competition, (4)) having a youth scientific group that is able to compete with similar groups from other schools, (5) having students selected as district, provincial and national level paskibraka, (6) developing a reading culture, (7) a culture of English and Arabic communication languages, (8) have an arts team that is ready to appear in every event whether for competition or non-competition, (9) have a sports team that can appear in inter-school competitions, (10) increase the use of information technology in learning, (11) have a cadre of preachers -reliable preacher, (12) the creation of a religious life in the madrasah environment which is demonstrated by sincere,

independent, simple behavior, brotherhood and creative freedom.

Work organization

Mathla'ul Anwar College is the center of educational activities in the Mathla'ul Anwar environment, which is under and responsible to the Mathla'ul Anwar Executive Board. The work organization at Madrasah Aliyah MA is structured based on the statutes that have been prepared. Madrasah Aliyah is under the auspices of the Mathaul Anwar Organization and is directly supervised by the Menes Central MA educational institution. The organization at Madrasah Aliyah is led by the Madrasah Head and assisted by deputy Madrasah Heads. The functional development of the Mathla'ul Anwar College is carried out by the Mathla'ul Anwar Executive Board who is in charge of Education.

Work supervision

Supervision and evaluation are carried out in the context of controlling the quality of education nationally as a form of accountability of education providers to interested parties. Evaluations are carried out on students, institutions and educational programs in formal and non-formal channels for all levels, units and types of education. Evaluation of student learning outcomes is carried out by educators to monitor the process, progress and improvement of student learning outcomes on an ongoing basis. Evaluation of students, educational units and educational programs is carried out by independent institutions on a regular, comprehensive, transparent and systemic basis to assess the achievement of national education standards. The Central Government and regional governments carry out evaluations of managers, units, pathways, levels and types of education. Society and/or professional organizations can form independent institutions to carry out evaluations. Provisions regarding evaluation as referred to above are further regulated following the applicable regulations.

Basic values of preparing a quality assurance strategy

The basic values in preparing a quality assurance strategy are based on the values contained in the Al-Qur'an, the Hadith of the Prophet, and the Khithah of Mathlul Anwar's struggle. The basic value system of the Islamic religion is used as a guide and direction for all educational processes and components in a comprehensive and holistic manner that emphasizes academic aspects (values reasoning), ideological-spiritual and behavioral aspects (values action). The system of values and beliefs that are believed to be the basis for carrying out work duties originates from the verses/dalil of naqliyah, namely the Qur'an and as-Sunnah. Mathlul Anwar's rationale for quality assurance is adapted to the values adhered to by educational institutions as guidelines for implementing education in Mathlul Anwar's environment, namely Philosophical Foundations, Mathlul Anwar's Khithah, Mathlul Anwar's AD/ART and Constitutional Foundations. The philosophical foundation underlies the basic principles and conceptual thinking that is based on the holy book Al-Qur'an and the

sunnah of the Prophet Muhammad. Mathlaul Anwar's Khithah is the basic concept of the blueprint for Mathlaul Anwar's movement in the fields of education and social religion. Mathlaul Anwar's AD/ART as the basis for the organization's movement in carrying out the work renewal movement and trying to advance universities in the social and educational fields. The constitutional basis is the legality of business in the education sector so that it is in accordance with the Laws of the Republic of Indonesia.

Quality assurance strategy by applying basic values to animate the vision and mission of Madrasah Aliyah. Core values are in accordance with important basic values, in this case Mathlaul Anwar's Khithah contains the basic values of the organization's struggle, namely producing a generation of Muslims who are aware of their responsibilities as caliphs on earth to build the nation and state. Education is expected to produce students who are strong in their faith, diligent in worship, have scientific skills, and are self-aware to build the environment and protect society from negative influences

DISCUSSION

Based on research on "Core Value-based Quality Assurance Strategy at Madrasah Aliyah Mathlaul Anwar, Menes Center, Banten", the researcher drew the following conclusions.

The strategic planning strategy for quality assurance at Madrasah Aliyah Mathlaul Anwar is based on educational research, analysis of facts, resource capabilities, financial resources, determining quality standards, determining alternative actions and methods of decision making so that the quality of education at Madrasah Aliyah Mathlaul Anwar Menes Center can be ensured have good quality. Market research and SWOT analysis really determine the direction of Total Quality Management that Madrasah Aliyah Mathlaul Anwar will carry out.

The preparation of the Madrasah Aliyah work program is prepared based on the direction of Khithah Mathlaul Anwar as a strategic guide, a basic guide to the philosophy of the organizational movement, the Statute of Mathlaul Anwar Educational Institutions, a guidebook for managing educational units, policy rules for implementing higher education and the Vision and Mission of Madrasah Aliyah so that it can guarantee the quality of education in Madrasah Aliyah Mathlaul Anwar Menes Center. The work program is strongly influenced by the core values that guide the organization. This can be seen in the strong religious atmosphere and the implementation of the organization's vision and mission in producing students who are capable in science and technology accompanied by competent religious knowledge, both in Islamic concepts and behavior. The work program is prepared by the head of the madrasah, the teacher council and the direction of the MA college every new academic year. The work program is always evaluated and improved, in terms of strengths and weaknesses, and implements modern management, namely independent madrasah-based management (MBM). Evidence of this

conclusion is that Madrasah Aliyah Matlaul Anwar has very good quality standards and is structured in terms of education.

The work organization at Madrasah Aliyah MA applies modern management concepts, using standard procedures that are adapted to core values to ensure the quality of student products. The organizational structure and division of tasks have been regulated and arranged based on work responsibilities, authority and workload. The placement of people according to their expertise is determined to carry out the tasks they will carry out so as to guarantee the quality of education at the Menes Central MA Madrasah Aliyah.

Supervision of work in the Madrasah Aliyah environment through the process of monitoring the implementation of learning so that work is in accordance with what was planned and if there are errors or deviations, corrections will be made. Work at the Mathlaul Anwar Madrasah Aliyah is always controlled and supervised by the education section of the Menes Center Mathlaul Anwar College. If there are errors and irregularities, the college will coordinate with the head of the Madrasah, so that it is in accordance with what has been planned in the Madrasah's annual program so that the quality of education is well maintained.

The basic value of preparing a quality assurance strategy greatly influences the performance of educators so that it encourages the behavior of teachers and madrasah employees to work as well as possible through understanding the correct faith and carrying out work as a form of devotion to Allah SWT and following the sunnah of the Prophet Muhammad SAW. The strategy of using core value at Mathlaul Anwar Madrasah is reflected in the large amount of religious content and local MA content which is a characteristic of the education program at Mathlaul Anwar so that the quality of Madrasah education has a competitive advantage.

Ethical approval: The research includes human participants and the data were collected upon receiving informed consent from the participants.

Consent to participate: The participants were informed the process of research report.

Availability of data: Data are available in the article.

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